

Development of choice preference theory in research

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Date submitted: January 23, 2014

Date accepted: June 30, 2014

Republished from:
Vasquez, B.A. (2014). Choice preference theory in research. *Journal of Institutional Research in South East Asia*, 12(1), 38-61.

ABSTRACT

The theoretical article atlases the theory of choice preference in research. This was initially induced from my experiences and supplemented with: (1) confessions from other researchers; and (2) available related literature. Classical and pragmatic grounded theory (GT) was exploited and modified to suit the need of the study. This type of GT is coined as “experience-based theory building”. Initially inductive, it amalgamated: (1) deduction; (2) abduction; and (3) retroduction. It obtained: (1) 13 Level I basic concepts: monetary, time, formal education, non-formal training, informal learning experience, exposure to alternative forms of research, no exposure to the alternative forms of research, acceptance, respect, disrespect, denial, open and close system; (2) 7 Level II subcategories or constructs: personal, socio-cultural, economic, educational, learning exposure, continuum of exposure to the alternative form of research tradition, action and acceptance system; and (3) 5 Level III theoretical categories: philosophical stance, influences, exposure, preferred research tradition and judgment. Choice preference was identified as the core category that interlaced the different theoretical categories, constructs and basic concepts. Choice preference is an individual process and cannot be imposed. The interaction between the acceptance system and exposure curbs the actions: (1) respect; (2) acceptance; (3) denial; and (4) disrespect. They are categorically interpreted as: (1) true wisdom; (2) informed; (3) ignorance; and (4) elitism. Choice preference engages with the: (1) expenditure to the preferred form; and (2) judgment to the alternative form. This is the synergy of learning exposure, spelled out in its formal, informal and non-formal form, and philosophical stance that is shaped by personal, economic, educational and socio-cultural influences.

Keywords: *choice preference, experience-induced, grounded theory, research*

I. INTRODUCTION

The theoretical article enunciates choice preference theory in research. This theory was induced from the: (1) researcher’s experience as a qualitative researcher being challenged by quantitative practitioners; (2) available related

literature regarding the debate between and within research traditions; and (3) experiences and insights of other practitioners. This theory is an attempt to put the quantitative-qualitative divide in academia to an end. Though argumentation helped in the development of both disciplines,

it also crops deleterious outcomes. This aims to curtail this circumstance with the foresight of budding knowledge uncompromised with unwarranted confinements. It is hoped that knowledge, theory and technology building will no longer be boxed-in unnecessarily.

The division between and within research paradigm/tradition has been observed since time immemorial. The hype of the quantitative-qualitative debate is centered in the diversity in philosophy and methodology (Reichardt & Cook, 1979; Bryman, 1984; Krantz, 1995; Steckler, McLeroy, Goodman, Bird & McCormick, 1992) and the discordancy in both paradigms (Gelo, Braackmann & Beneka, 2008; Rosenberg, 1988; Noblit & Hare, 1988; Lincoln & Guba, 1985). Each paradigm/tradition claim superiority over the other compromising utilization of outputs. This caused confusion on the part of novice researchers and consumers. Though some would resort to a more pragmatic locus (Gelo, Braakmann & Benetka, 2008; Tasharkkori & Teddlie, 1998), others still sustain the dogma of its pure nature. This debate is also observed within a specific research tradition. Glaser together with Strauss discovered grounded theory methodology (1967/2006). They both diverge after disagreeing

in some procedural stances (Strauss & Corbin, 1990; Glaser, 1992). This also happened to Wacquant (2002), Anderson (2002), and Duneier (1999) with their opinions in the use of *a priori*, *posteriori* or a combination of both.

Currently, no theory is fashioned to describe, predict and control this circumstance in research. Though pragmatic approaches are available, others still do not subscribe to this idea. The reason may lie behind the failure to understand the dynamics, process and meaning of each position. This paper may be able to bridge the gap hoping to limit, if not stop, this unfavorable circumstance.

II. DOMAIN OF INQUIRY

The purpose of the study is to develop a substantive theory grounded from the: (a) challenges I experienced as a qualitative researcher from quantitative adjudicators; (b) quantitative-qualitative debate; and (c) debate within specific research tradition. Furthermore, it attempts to transcend the substantive theory to formal theory.

III. METHOD

This utilized Experience-induced Grounded

Table 1. Sampling frame

Source	Unit sampled	Sampling design	Remarks or sampling frame
Personal Experience n = 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Autosampling (purposive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commencing point only To draw initial concepts with or without properties
Interviews or Brain Storming Activity n = 6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidents Philosophical Assumptions of Researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical Sampling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To draw more concepts or develop properties of the identified concepts Criteria based from previous conceptualization Informants must have experienced or observed the philosophical debates between or within research paradigms
Literature n = 231 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Books Journal Articles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidents or cases Philosophical Arguments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Theoretical Sampling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To draw more concepts or develop properties of the identified concepts Criteria based from previous conceptualization Cases or philosophical debates between and/or within research paradigms

Theory as a research tradition. Specifically, this is an offshoot of classical (Glaser & Strauss, 1967/2006) and pragmatic (Charmaz, 2006) Grounded Theory (GT). What makes this method novel is that it commences from the researcher's experience as a starting point. Initially, one would think that it is not GT but a specialized form of autoethnography. However, this does not deviate from the principle of classical GT. The autoethnographic feature of this research provides descriptive data for abstracting a theory. The autoethnographic part is only a portion of what I coin as "Experience-induced GT". The descriptive portion (a) is not yet GT but a means of organizing data for initial GT analysis and (b) can be reported separately as autoethnography. The actual GT is when the descriptions of the autoethnography are reanalyzed in a GT process.

Sampling. The challenges encountered as a qualitative researcher with quantitative researchers were culled purposively as a commencing point. Theoretical sampling allowed me to engage in: (a) informal interviews with individuals who had similar experience and deviant viewpoints; and (b) in culling secondary data from books and articles regarding quantitative-qualitative debate, as well as debates within specific research traditions.

"Retroductive data analysis is like dancing the *cha-cha-cha*. The inductive processes are the forward *chasses*, the deductive processes are the backward *chasses*, and the abductive processes are the non-directional *chasses*. Each step taken fostered the theoretical *finesse*."

Brian A. Vasquez, 2013

Data Analysis. Data analysis is patterned from the recommendation of Glaser and Strauss (1967/2006), and Charmaz (2006) with modification to: (1) suit the need of my exploration; and (2) incorporate my personal philosophical stances. Open coding was done to analyze the autoethnographic data to induce

concepts for theoretical exploration. Constant comparative analysis was done to related entries in the autoethnographic narrative. Along with the coding process, memos were drafted to document the analytic process. Induction is only an initial process of the analysis. Along the way, the researcher (Hillier, 2010): (1) verified data deductively; and (2) explored the data abductively (Kapitan, 1992). I believe that abducting data broadens knowledge by making sense from nothing (data collected without *a priori*) objectively (Habermas, 1978) culminating the introduction of new ideas (Meyer & Lunnay, 2013). In other words, a retroductive process was employed (Wallace, 1971). The chase of induction and deduction nourished the theory-building process.

Theoretical sampling of other pertinent data was done to: (1) arrive in data saturation; (2) validate or confirm concepts; and (3) deduce frameworks memoed from induced concepts. These transcripts were derived from: (1) multiple formal and informal interviews; (2) brainstorming exercise; and (3) existing literature. These printed resources were not considered as a review material but as data for GT analysis. Constant comparative analysis was done as narratives existing texts and transcripts that were accumulated. Memoing was engaged at each stopover in the coding process.

Selective or focused coding emerged after the core category was identified (Holton, 2010). Irrelevant codes were dropped while germane codes were retained.

Theoretical coding was then employed to entwine each part of the puzzle. In this study, I employed concept mapping (Wheeldon & Faubert, 2009) to get rid of too much narrative explanation. This stratagem increased the power of abstraction and relational explanation of concepts in a schematic form.

IV. IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHOICE PREFERENCE THEORY

The initial focus of the research was on

Table 2. Formulated Codes

Core Category	Category: Theoretical Constructs Level III	Sub Category: Constructs Level II	Basic Concept Level I
Choice Preference	Philosophical Stance		
	Influences	Personal	
		Socio-Cultural	
		Economic	Monetary Time
		Educational (Equated with Exposure)	
	Exposure (Equated with Educational)	Learning Exposure	Formal education
			Non-formal training
			Informal learning experience
		Continuum of exposure to the alternative forms of research tradition	Exposed to alternative form of research Not exposed to alternative form of research
	Preferred Research Tradition		
	Judgment	Action	Acceptance
			Respect
			Disrespect
			Denial/Refusal/ Confusion
		Acceptance Systems	Open system Close system

Note: *Educational Influence* is spelled out as *Exposure* for its major contribution in the choice.

the challenges encountered by qualitative researchers. As data were constantly compared to each other, the substantive theory of choice preference in research was induced. Commencing with induction, saturated with deduction, and enriched with abduction and retrogression, the original focus transcended into the concept of choice preference, which has formal application in learning and personality.

V. DEFINING THE CONCEPTS IN CHOICE PREFERENCE THEORY

I would like to begin by defining the following terminologies using their formal theoretical application. Its substantive definition will be presented in the discussion:

1. Preference is the psychological evaluative

judgment in the awareness of liking or disliking (Scherer, 2005) an idea;

2. Continuum of exposure is the gamut between being acquainted (exposed) or not (not exposed) with an idea:

a. No exposure is the state of being not in contact with an idea;

b. Exposure is the state of being in contact with an idea;

i. Learning exposure is the state of being in contact with an idea that allowed the individual to learn something which can be classified as (OECD, 1996/2010):

1. Formal education is the system of organized and institutionalized learning that involves

- predetermined purpose and curriculum;
- 2. Non-formal education is a decentralized and organized system of learning earned thru anarchistic (e.g. free schooling), alternative (e.g. trainings, seminars and workshops), autodidactical (e.g. self-directed learning) or vocational (e.g. direct and specific practical training) systems;
- 3. Informal learning experience is an unorganized form of learning thru experience;
- ii. Exposed to the alternative form is the state of being acquainted to another form aside from the preferred form;
- c. Judgment is the appraisal of evidence to arrive in a preferred choice influenced by the acceptance system resulting to an action;
 - i. Action is the process of performing acceptance, respect, disrespect, denial or refusal in the realization of an intention;
 - 1. Acceptance is the action of agreeing or consenting;
 - 2. Respect is the action of regard;
 - 3. Disrespect is the action of disregard;
 - 4. Denial or Refusal is the action of rejection;
 - ii. Acceptance System is the bipolarity between being open or close to an idea;
 - 1. Open System is the openness to an idea rather than the preferred form;
 - 2. Close System is the blindness to an alternative idea and ethnocentricness to the preferred form;
- d. Influences are personal, socio-cultural, economic and educational dispositions or familiarities that have the capacity to produce an effect on the formation of the individual's philosophical stance;
 - i. Personal Influence is the individual's topographies, experiences, inclinations and demographics that contributed his personal philosophical stance;
 - ii. Socio-Cultural Influence is the common agreed inclination or pressure that influence the formation of the individual's philosophical stance;
 - iii. Economic Influence is the willingness

Figure 1. Theoretical coding: Choice Preference Theory in research

- of the individual to spend money and time that affect the construction of the individual's philosophical stance;
- iv. Educational Influence is synonymous with exposure; it is the utilization of what was learned formally, informally and non-formally that influence the formation of the individual's philosophical stance;
 - e. Philosophical Stance is the personal way of viewing reality, phenomenon or circumstance (worldview).

VI. The Ideal Scenario

Ideally, the choice of what research tradition, design and method to use in the conduct of any investigation are dictated by the domain of inquiry or research problem. How to generate the answer to specific research question determines the tasks to undertake. In the ground, researchers and research adjudicators, at times, trail apart from this ideal set-up. The substantive theory discussed below attempts to explain the processes involved in this kind of phenomenon.

VII. THE CHOICE PREFERENCE THEORY IN RESEARCH: A SUBSTANTIVE THEORY

I would like to scrounge some concepts from economics. According to Peters (2008), the foundation of all choice theory is preference relation. When given two alternatives, one will try to pick one based from personal preference. Mandler (2000) claimed that rational choices allow an individual to choose an alternative that can provide him greatest pleasure. This utilitarian concept dwells in the idea that promotes self-welfare.

Although Peter's claim is useful in understanding my own theory, I doubt if the concept of utility and self-welfare, as explained by Mandler, is covered by my theory. While the concept of pleasure is still applicable, the operationalization of pleasure in my theory is defined as inclination, which may not necessarily indicate utility and self-welfare.

The mentioned theories were identified after the conceptualization of the choice preference

theory in research. Although there are similarities, the theory I created have practical and substantive application in the researcher's choice of design and method. Knowledge of the economic concept of choice preference may be necessary in understanding my theory. However, my focus dwells in determining choice preference and its resultant action, which departs from utility and self-welfare. Rationality is then operationalized as the synergy between philosophical stance and exposure, which does not automatically mean beneficial. Proclivity is emphasized here more than utility. It is the appetite to consume something that gives comfort and pleasure. Pleasure then is not equated with functional welfare, as claimed by most choice preference theory in economics, but cognitive gratification. Cognitive gratification acts towards appetitive results and denies aversive upshots. A more comfortable form of knowledge is preferred over something ambiguous to maximize hedonism and minimize discomfort.

This theory describes and explains the influences that help shape the individual's actions. Additionally, this will help predict certain choices. When transcended to its formal form, this has a practical value to education and psychology since it covers a construct on learning. This can also be utilized in other fields, which I failed to identify.

Proposition 1. *The synergy between the researcher's philosophical stance and learning exposure determines his preferred research tradition*

You will notice that I repeatedly use the word synergy instead of amalgamation in this paper. Amalgamation refers to the summation of components, while synergy is more than just summation. The combined effect is greater than the sum of its components. In Gestalt psychology, we say, "*the whole is greater than the sum of its parts*" (Smutts, 1926).

The preferred research tradition is driven by his personal philosophical stance. A philosophical stance is a personal position that requires the researcher to answer the how of things and demands to riposte the why and what (Holden & Lynch, 2004). The development of this standpoint

requires the person to formulate copious central assumptions concerning the nature of reality (ontology), knowledge (epistemology), values (axiology) and methodology (Burrell & Morgan, 1979; Polit & Beck, 2008; Creswell, 2007). The researcher may not necessarily be conceptually conscious about this. This may operate reflexively as revealed by his belief system on how, what and why to operate things. The synergy of these central assumptions is consequential to each other (Holden & Lynch, 2004) and manifested by the researchers' actions. This paper will not dissect the explanation of these assumptions since it is beyond its focus. I suggest that the reader will do further perusal of available literature concerning these concepts.

Figure 2. Axial Coding: Influences to Philosophical Stance

Proposition 2. Philosophical stance is the synergy of personal, economic, socio-cultural and educational influences

The philosophical stance is also a synergy of different influences. These are personal, socio-cultural, economic and educational dispositions or familiarities.

Personal. The characteristics of the researcher including his background and inclinations help form his philosophy: (a) personal values illustrate the axiological assumption; (b) personal relations shape the researcher's epistemological and methodologic assumption; and (c) personal belief shapes his ontological assumption. These then moderate in the choice preference to a particular research

tradition. ^aIf the researcher follows stringent ethical dogmas; he is likely to choose a positivistic over a naturalistic approach. ^bIf the researcher is more comfortable with interaction; he is likely to choose qualitative over quantitative approach. ^cIf the researcher is highly empirical and objective, and acknowledges that there is a single reality, he is likely to choose quantitative over qualitative approach. The enumerations are only samples and not the only existing reality. It only provides as an idea on how these influences help shape the researcher's philosophical stance.

Socio-cultural. The society and its culture influence the researcher's philosophical assumption. This then moderates in the choice preference to a particular research tradition. What is communally accepted is commonly cogitated as an agreement reality (Rubin & Babbie, 2001) and most of the time viewed as dogmatic. In an academic culture where quantitative research is a predominantly accepted method, an attempt to do a qualitative research is usually subjected to scrutiny using quantitative criteria. What is preferred is something that everyone else thinks is the only way to do things. If the researcher would like to challenge what is normative, then he likely desired for an unfamiliar approach and prepared himself for academic argumentation.

Economic. The preferred stance may be motivated by austerity measures in time and resource. If a researcher has the luxury of time interpreting transcriptions, then he might choose qualitative over quantitative. Although it does not follow all the time that quantitative research is speedier over qualitative, the researcher will likely pick a method (qualitative or quantitative) that matches with time expenditure. This also holds true with the alacrity of the researcher to expend resources. If the researcher has the lavishness of funds, then that researcher will pick a method that is high-priced. Otherwise, the researcher will prefer an approach that fits the availability of coffers. The presentation may not directly socket as philosophical stance. But if we try to ground it with axiological and methodological postulations, it would make sense. The choice of method is clearly or indistinguishably driven by economic

(synonymous with resource in this study) considerations. How the researcher values time and cost are definitely motivated with his personal axiological conjecture.

Methodological choice may be directly or indirectly predisposed by economic reasons. In sampling for example, the more time and funds you have, the more number of samples you will get. The more time and funds you have, the likely you will design a methodological frame that will consume more time and expense. Although some would prefer a better option for a method, in some cases, a researcher may opt for the alternative form when time and resource will not allow. This may be one of the reasons why pragmatism in research emerged. Considering the concept of utilitarianism, what can provide much benefit is chosen after cogitating all aspects.

Educational. This segment, though part of the influences, is highlighted for its key involvement in explaining the theory. As you can observe in figure 1, it is singled out from the construct of influences.

The discussion of exposure is subdivided into two subcategories: (1) learning exposure; and (2) continuum of exposure.

Figure 3. Axial Coding: Exposure

Proposition 3. Exposure to the different form of research tradition is the interaction between the continuum of exposure and synergy of learning exposures.

When abstracting these concepts during one of my memoing sessions, I have realized that this

theory is not only a theory of research. It is also a theory of learning and personality. Transcending the conception into its formal form (isolating its substantial application to research), it has practical application to any field especially in education and psychology.

Exposure is a continuum from exposed to not exposed. A researcher is likely inclined to choose a method that he is acquainted. It is practically obvious that few would pick a certain stratagem that is unfamiliar. However, there are instances wherein a person challenges himself to progress utilizing unfamiliar methods. Initially, you may think that the person is not exposed to this scheme. One must realize that this is a continuum. In the process of acquaintance with the new stratagem, learning occurs. Learning as an action directs accumulative exposure to that system. The accumulation of familiarities with the new information leads him to the pole away from ignorance.

Figure 4. Axial Coding: Continuum of Exposure to the Alternative Form of Research

In adjudicating the alternative form of research, one is likely to renounce it. The acceptability of the other form of research is highly dependent on the individual's exposure to that alternative form. Let us say a researcher is positivistic but has knowledge of naturalistic inquiry, that scientist is likely to respect the legitimacy of naturalism. However, this is not always the case if the knowledge of that researcher is limited or zero. Although exposure of the alternative form can shape its acceptability, other factors may curb the phenomenon that allows the researcher to disrespect the cogency of the other paradigm regardless of exposure. This tends to ensue among purists. This will be explained later in the text.

Figure 5. Axial Coding: Learning Exposure of Research

Postulate 1. Learning exposure is the synergy of the researcher's formal, informal and non-formal learning experience.

Exposure is an extensive construct that can be dissected into (OECD, 2010): (a) formal; (b) informal; and (c) non-formal. I will borrow the definition from the Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order No. 8 Series of 2009: (1) *formal training* refers to the hierarchically structured and chronologically graded learning organized and provided by the formal school system and for which certification is required in order for the learner to progress through the grades or move higher levels (BP 232); (2) *informal learning* is incidental learning that results from life experiences, workplace-based learning, volunteer activities, self-directed learning, family responsibilities, and others; and (3) *non-formal learning* is intentional and gained by the individual through participation in organized workplace-based training, non-credit courses and workshops the completion of which does not lead to receiving formal credit.

Learning exposure is the synergy of the researcher's formal, informal and non-formal learning experiences. The theories and practical knowledge derived are more than the amalgamation of the three forms. When new information is derived, it is processed by the individual, which results in either acquiescent to the new knowledge, with or without unlearning previous information, or dismissal to the new gen. The pool of learning then influences the

researcher's philosophical inclination. This guides him in picking the preferred research method.

Figure 6. Axial Coding: Choice Preference

Proposition 4. The researcher's preferred form of research tradition and his judgment towards the alternative form contain his choice preference.

There are two basic concepts of engagement that slice-up choice preference, which purports to: (1) expend the preferred form of research; and (2) judge the alternative form of research. This must not be seen as a dichotomy. It is in fact consumed simultaneously. For example, a naturalistic researcher (*preference*) that evaluates a positivistic paper recognizes the rigor of the work (*judgment*) since he is exposed to the criteria in evaluating scientific-empirical papers (most of the time quantitative in nature). Paradoxically, a quantitative researcher (*preference*), who is a pure positivist, magistrates a qualitative report as invalid and unreliable (*judgment*) since he evaluates the rigor of the report based on quantitative criteria, regardless of his exposure to this kind of work. The former example is further supported with:

Proposition 5. The exposure of the researcher to the alternative form of research determines his action towards it.

Before discussing Preposition 5, allow me to enumerate the following properties so as to avoid confusion and dogmatic interpretation:

1. Researchers and research adjudicators operate in both system;
2. No researcher and adjudicator solely observe a single system;
3. There is always a dominant system operating; and
4. The system operating at a certain time-point is primarily dependent to certain conditions.

The following conditions are identified:

1. Person-referent condition – How credible is the source of information?
2. Context-referent condition – How credible is the information?
3. Self-referent condition – I know better than you!
4. Combination of all or any of the identified conditions.

A researcher always has a preferred form of research shaped by his philosophical stance. It does not necessarily follow that if a researcher has a preferred form, he is likely to dismiss the alternative. Judging the alternative form is shaped by his learning exposure. The more exposed the researcher to it, the less likely it is dismissed. Take note that I use the word less likely since there is another construct that curbs the phenomenon. The model as shown below will explicate this:

Figure 7. Axial Coding: System of Acceptance or Denial of Alternative Research Tradition

Postulate 2. An open system ranges from respect to acceptance of the alternative form of research.

Postulate 3. A close system ranges from disrespect to denial of the alternative form of research.

Human being operates in two types of systems: (a) open; and (b) close. When a researcher is open to the alternative form of research tradition he may respond by: (1) respecting; and/or (2) accepting the alternative. In respecting, the researcher maintains his personal preference while recognizing the rigor of the other form. In accepting, the researcher tends to assimilate in practice the alternative form without discounting the preference. In some rare cases, the researcher may partially disengage to the initial preference. Considering that the person is open-minded, disengagement to the previous preference does not necessarily imply total rejection, but only a change in *panache* and still with credence of the reputation of the former. When the researcher is close-minded to the alternative form, the initial reaction is disrespect towards total denial. In disrespect, the researcher is acquainted with the rigor of the alternative form but still dogmatically insist with his bias. Denial happens when the researcher denounces the integrity of the other form. In denial, the researcher may have full to partial acquaintance or totally ignorant to the alternative form. Nonetheless, all operates in a mechanism wherein information is thrown either by: (1) not recognizing the legitimacy and rigor of the alternative after conceptually learning and understanding it; or (2) closing the door to learn and understand the alternative.

According to Hare (2003), the axiology of open-mindedness is acknowledged since the time of Socrates:

“I am not speaking dogmatically from the certainty of assured knowledge. I am simply your fellow-explorer in the search for truth, and if somebody who contradicts me is obviously right, I shall

be the first to give way.”

Socrates in Plato’s *Gorgias*, 506

Hare (2003) further claimed that this Socratic philosophy is reverberated by several philosophers like: (a) John Stuart Mill (1859), who asserts that judgment is trusted from people open to criticisms; (b) C. S. Peirce, who suggested to throw our personal belief the moment new learnt elements are inconsistent (Hartshorne, C., & Weiss, P, 1931); and (c) Bertrand Russell (1950), who claimed that dismissing openness is dangerous. These statements are further dissected in the subsequent models.

Figure 8. Pre Metric Modeling: Judgment Matrix of the Alternative Form of Research Tradition (Substantive Form)

Let X axis be the range of exposure and Y axis the close-open system continuum. This will produce four quadrants: (1) respect; (2) acceptance; (3) disrespect; and (4) denial. These quadrants represent the actions taken by the researcher. With this model, we can derive the following qualitatively verified hypotheses (as per Glaser and Strauss’ [1967/2006, p.39-40], this must be noted as a suggestion, confirmed with theoretically sampled and constantly compared evidence; this is not statistically tested with excessive pile of proof):

Hypothesis 1. The more open and exposed the researcher to the alternative form of research the more he accepts or recognizes it.

Hypothesis 2. The more closed and unexposed the researcher to the alternative form of research the more he denies or refuses it

Hypothesis 3. The more closed and unexposed the researcher to the alternative form of research the more he is confused and thus denies and refuses it.

Hypothesis 4. If the researcher is open but unexposed to the alternative form of research he tends to respect it and eventually accepts and recognizes it.

Hypothesis 5. If the researcher is closed but

Figure 9. Choice Preference Theory: The Formal Theory

exposed to the alternative form of research he tends to disrespect it and eventually denies and refuses it.

VIII. Choice Preference Theory : A Formal Theory

Figures 9 and 10 are the translated models for formal use. The theory can be utilized in areas other than research, *exempli gratia* preferred teaching method among teachers. The preferred form is shaped by the teacher’s background, philosophical stance and learning exposure, and his judgment on the applicability of a certain method is dependent on the synergy of all factors *vis-à-vis* his open close system spectrum and learning exposure continuum. This theory can also be consumed to explain the preferred: (1) school of thought; (2) counseling technique; (3) therapy; (4) mode of treatment; and (5) many more.

Although humans operate in both, there is always a dominant system functioning. We can then classify individuals based from their dominant system. The following are the hypothesis with explanation of the interpretation:

Hypothesis 6. When the person is open and unexposed, that person exhibits true wisdom

In true wisdom, a person is able to process the information and learn from it even though he has no previous exposure to the information. The selective analysis, as a result of the value of respect without disregarding bias, allows the person to comprehend rationally which assists him to become more informed.

“The only true wisdom is in knowing you know nothing.”

Socrates

Figure 10. Pre Metric Modeling: Judgment Matrix (Formal Form)

Figure 11. Categorical Interpretation Based from the Judgment Matrix

I recalled one of my lecturers shared that the only way to understand something new-fangled is to empty the *demitasse*. A full cup can no longer accommodate something new. This does not imply that our cups need to be empty. Along the interspaces between the matters in our cups are gaps that accommodate new learning. If we insist that our cups are full, it can no longer sip new ideas and learning do not occur. This wastes the chances of utilizing something relevant. Information may not be pertinent at the first squint; it will be when understood well. It may not be significant now, but may be in the near future.

Hypothesis 7. When the person is open and exposed, that person is well informed and is able to transcend the information to practice

Well-informed individuals tend to judge accordingly and are able to compartmentalize personal biases with existing logical alternative systems. This individual can segregate information with respect and values the alternative forms as valid and reliable options to undertake. Although

there are always preferences, the ability to put on an alternative lens to be able to see the rigor of the other form is appreciated. This type of individual is able to effectively and selectively appreciate the value of the information and transform this evidence into practice.

Being well-informed is not the same as know it all (Swain, 2009). Swain added that being knowledgeable implicates awareness about loads of diverse information, while being a know-all may implicate knowing all there is to know about a phenomenon. When one broadens interest to something beyond the boundaries of his interest allows the person to be well-informed. This provides him a chance of providing good insights and judgment and not boxed in to an exclusive system.

Hypothesis 8. When the person is close and exposed, that person overly accentuating elitism

“A society’s attitudes to innate intelligence are closely correlated with its levels of inequality.”

Danny Dorling, 2010

A word first known in 1947, elitism is defined by Merriam-Webster (2013) as “consciousness of being or belonging to an elite”. This consciousness leads to exclusivity. These groups looked only after their own interest and encouraged powerlessness and unresponsiveness to the non-affiliates (Wasserman, 2006). Dorling (2010) believed that IQism influences this phenomenon. IQism defines elitism with its history, but I personally believed it had changed over time. I would like to see elitism now as a claimed privilege among established groups. Although in antiquity, this was fashioned among intellectuals, with the advent of knowledge-for-all, a number of clued-up individuals with differently inclined school of thoughts groomed. Those who prefer the most well established and accepted thought will compromise the elite group while the rest are marginalized. Given this scenario, IQism

still played a role. However, it is no longer a divide between the knowledgeable vs the rest, but is already a combat between who is more: (1) intelligent; and (2) legitimate scholar. When elitism is highlighted, this leads him to look as if he is ignorant to the alternate form. Ignorance here is not defined as “not knowing anything”, but is the failure to appreciate the authenticity of the alternative form and demonstrating “as if he is ignorant”. This type of ethnocentrism (Leininger & McFarland, 2005) is the plaintiff of the “know-it-all” group (Swain, 2009). The claimed superiority of knowledge is actually the ignorance or cultural-blindness of the realities beyond their preferred boundaries.

Hypothesis 9. When the person is close and unexposed, that person is ignorant

Ignorance may lead to judgment from uncertainty. Perry (2008), Kahneman and Tversky (1996), and Lichtenstein and Fischhoff (1977) suggested that individuals engaged in empirical studies often trust that they are knowledgeable beyond what they actually do. This type of mindset would usually direct to unfavorable consequences. Overconfidence about their knowledge and ability shaped the partialities in judgment and decision-making. Perry (2008) suggested that ignorance trails the individual to be less cautious in their decision-making. In most cases, what is unfamiliar is less accepted and what is familiar is preferred as the superior form. As cited by Smithson (1997), empirical studies in the late 70’s regarding the “Catch-All Underestimation Bias” (Fischhoff, Slovic & Lichtenstein, 1978) signposted that when alternatives are unclear people tend to underestimate it. Individuals verge not to face risk of committing error. They avoid in gambling on an option especially when there is lack of information (Frisch & Baron, 1988).

“Open-mindedness is properly thought of as a kind of critical receptiveness in which our willingness to

consider new ideas is guided by our best judgment with respect to the available evidence. Genuine open-mindedness requires finding some middle ground between being ready to entertain every idea seriously and being excessively resistant to reasonable possibilities. This line of thought suggests a natural connection with an Aristotelian account of virtue as involving a mean[s] between two extremes to be determined by the use of practical wisdom (Nicomachean Ethics, 1107). We may go too far in the direction of critical skepticism and lose sight of open-mindedness; but it is no mark of open-mindedness to be willing to embrace absurdity, to be unwilling ever to draw a conclusion, or to be ready to abandon a promising line of inquiry merely to pursue some other possibility. There may be a sense in which the merits of open-mindedness are obvious, but the confusions outlined above suggest, as Oliver Wendell Holmes (1921) reminded us, that there are circumstances in which what is needed is an education in the obvious (Hare, 2002)."

Hare, 2003

IX. REFLECTION

The debate between research traditions will only stop when scrutinizers have an open mind. This is probably the reason why Glaser constantly emphasized the concept of "open-mindedness" (Lillemor & Hallberg, 2010). Although, Glaser (1992) argues with the prescriptions of Strauss and Corbin (1996), I acknowledged the motivation of the argument. Prescriptions hinder the researcher's scholarship. Glaser and Strauss (1967/2006) emphasized that one, "should not curb anyone's creativity... they should encourage it". This includes creating original methods and ideas. Glaser (2006) emphasized that a researcher, especially a PhD candidate, must observe total autonomy, originality and contribution. Scholarly

contribution is limited or slayed when autonomy and originality is compromised.

X. CONCLUSION IN METAPHOR

Choice preference is the synergy of formal, non-formal and informal learning experiences together with the individual's philosophical stance. Judgment is shaped by the synergy of exposure and the openness or closeness of the individual to the new information. It is stressed that choice preference is a personal process and it must not be imposed to another individual. This statement is best captured in the Gestalt Prayer:

"I do my thing and you do your thing.

I was not born in this world to live up to your expectations

And neither are you to live up to mine...

If by chance we meet up, it is fine and beautiful.

But if not, it cannot be helped

Because I am simply I and you are simply you."

Fritz Perls, 1969, p. 4

Although the metaphor emphasized on multiplicity of realities that causes differences in preference, it also stresses the importance of acknowledging the alternative form. It is not an egotistical standpoint that pressures self-absorbed sovereignty. Just like the Gestalt Prayer, it teaches us not to ineptly impose our own stance to others nor allow others to impose their stance to us. In that way, debates are prevented. In any facets in life, whether choice of research methodology or strategies in teaching style, one must realize the importance of dissimilarities as a mode for development: (1) disagreements allow each perspective to see opportunities towards competitive improvement; (2) diverse opinions permit the emergence of new ideas that help improve practice in any profession; and (3) dissimilar schools of thought break the monotony in knowledge. In totality, it signals more explorations to expand, refine and develop a body of knowledge.

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